

Contribution of Patiala State in the Second World War (1939-1945)

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Abstract

Patiala, one of the major Sikh Princely States of British India, played a significant role in the British war effort during Second World War. Military contribution supported through Indian expeditionary leadership initiative. This paper examines the broader Contribution and impacts of political, military involvement and Patiala's participation. Which also describes changes in agricultural production, wartime inflation and military service. It also examines how wartime loyalty to the British influenced the position of the Raj during the final stages of colonial rule and its eventual integration into independent India. The state's contribution has often been overlooked due to its location in both the imperial and regional contexts, Patiala played a significant role in sustaining cooperative efforts and shaping the transition from princely rule to democratic rule in north India.

Keywords

Patiala State, Civic Guard, War Board, Second World War.

Introduction

Patiala State continued its tradition of providing military assistance to the British Empire and Played a Significant and loyal role in Second World War. Under the leadership of Maharaja Yadvinder Singh, the state contributed significant manpower, funds and specialized units to the Allied War effort, earning high praise from the British government.¹ Patiala State was one of the important princely states in the Punjab region, ruled by the Phulkian dynasty. During the Second World War, the ruler of the state was Maharaja Yadvinder Singh, who was also a princely state under the British Empire. The Maharaja was expected to support British military operations. As soon as England decided to employ Indians in various battlefields, the Punjab State immediately offered its military services, which the British government accepted. Patiala State's contribution was the highest among the princely states of Punjab. The Patiala State Army fought on various fronts and earned high praise from the British government.²

Objective of study

1. To Analyze the Military contribution of Patiala State.
2. To Examine the economic and material support provided by the state, such as financial aid, war funds etc.
3. To evaluate the role of leadership particularly the role of Maharaja Yadvinder Singh.
4. To assess the Impacts of war participation on the Patiala Soldiers,-in the terms of recruitment economic changes.

Review of Literature

1. Ian Copeland in his book 'Princely States and the Raj' examines the broader political role of princely states. Copeland argues that the loyalty of these states in times of war was a strategic decision to secure their autonomy and prestige within the colonial structure. While his work offers theoretical insights, it does not focus specifically on Patiala.
2. William Lee Warner in his Work, The Protected Princes of India, portrays the princely states as loyal allies under British sovereignty, with limited autonomy. His colonial perspective explains the cooperation the states like Patiala in imperial wars, though it ignores indigenous perspectives and the social consequences.

Main Text

The early history of the Patiala Army is unclear. Either no formal records were kept, or they were lost during the various upheavals and invasions that swept the region. However surviving fragment's indicate that from the region of Maharaja Baba Ala Singh, the Army consisted mostly of cavalry.³ In Earlier times, military organization in Patiala was based on the establishment of a camp under the leadership of a *Risaldar*. There is an unconfirmed claim that Patiala once had approximately 500 forts, each commanded by a *Jamadar*, who maintained a small contingent of infantry for defense.⁴ The Civil administration of districts called *Thanas*, was overseen by *Thanedars*, who also had military responsibilities, managing a force of 50 cavalry and 50

infantry to maintain law and order. These highest command of the army was held by the *Bakshi*, or Commander-in-chief. During the region of Maharaja Sahib Singh, the importance of infantry was officially recognized, resulting in the formation of the first infantry battalion.⁵

The army expanded further under Maharaja Karam Singh. Five more infantry battalions, each consisting of 1000 soldiers, were formed. Horse mounted artillery units were also created, supporting the traditional use elephant, ox and camel drawn cannons. Thus the marshal of the lance of the Patiala army is steeped in a rich and evolving history, defined by strong leadership, a disciplined structure and a deep warrior spirit. It was to recognize the military strength of the states that the then Viceroy of India, Lord Dufferin, issued an important proclamation on the occasion of Maharaja Rajendra Singh's wedding in 1888.⁶

Maharaja Rajendra Singh raised a force of 600 cavalry and 1,000 infantry for imperial service. The following year, 200 more men were added to the infantry, dividing it into two regiments. It was during this reorganization that the 1st Rajendra Lancers.⁷ The Rajendra Lancers fighting during First World War brought the regiment everlasting honor and respect. The government of India accepted the service of eight companies of the Patiala imperial service infantry and four cavalry units from the state.⁸

The most important feature of Patiala lies in the warrior spirit of its people. Known as the nursery of warriors and soldiers, the state has long been recognized for its strong military tradition. In view of this heritage, it was natural for the state to take deliberate steps to preserve this proud legacy and support the sponsors of those who sacrificed their lives while upholding the traditions of valor and bravery. In line with this concept, a Central soldier's board was set up, with branches established in each district, to ensure coordinated welfare efforts for serving and ex-servicemen and their families. On 22 November 1939, while inaugurating the soldier's board, Maharaja Yadvinder Singh stressed the importance of this initiative and expended confidence that the board would greatly benefit the countless people of Patiala who had embraced the profession of soldier with great valor and bravery.⁹ He paid tribute to the 28000 soldiers of Patiala who shed their blood in various theatres of the great war of 1914. Acknowledging the bravery and sacrifice. The establishment of the soldier's board was a step towards ensuring that these soldiers and their families receive continued support and recognition. The main responsibilities of the soldier's board were clearly outlined during the ceremony.¹⁰

These functions included ensuring the welfare of the families of ex-servicemen and currently serving soldiers promoting goodwill between the civilian and military communities and assisting the chairman of the district soldier's board in managing administrative matters relating to ex-servicemen and their dependents. The board was also tasked with encouraging cooperation between ex-servicemen to local civilian authorities. Furthermore, the board was responsible for assisting the children of ex-servicemen in securing educational benefits and for providing full support to the district level leadership in improving the functioning of ex-servicemen welfare initiatives. The Defence services of the state were organized under the direct supervision of the Maharaja, who had complete authority over the Patiala State Army. He was supported by a well-organized military administration headed by the Commander-in-chief, assisted by senior officers such as the chief of the General Staff, the Quartermaster General and the Education General. For administrative convenience, the entire territory of Patiala State was divided into six districts (*Nizamats*) and seven sub divisions, ensuring better administration and coordination, especially in matters related to defence, military training and welfare services. This integrated approach highlighted the Maharaja's commitment to military efficiency and the complete care of his soldiers and their families.¹¹

The boundaries of these systems are the same for both judicial and revenue purposes. At the head of each system is a Nazim Audit Deputy Commissioner who combines both judicial and administrative powers in himself, as was the case in British India. The Nazims is assisted in this administration by Nazims, who exercise the powers of a magistrate. When the Second World War broke out in the early Spring of 1939, the then Prime Minister, Nawab Sir Liaquat Hayat Khan, went on a long leave of absence due to ill health. The Maharaja decided to assume the office of Prime Minister and continued to perform the duties of the office until the Nawab's return at the end of August. The international situation was deteriorating day by day and war was declared and soon after the declaration of the Second World War in 1939, Maharaja Yadvinder Singh sent a telegram to the Viceroy of India and said:¹²

"I avail myself of this opportunity to renew my unwavering and steadfast loyalty to the throne and person of my royal state and to abide by this declaration with all my might which reflects

the proud warlike traditions of the Patiala House, whose loyalty to the Crown Prince has been tested by many important tests. While fighting against the forces of darkness and aggression I need not add that the sudden offer made by me earlier is not limited to the crisis of September 1938 but is good for all emergencies.”

Establishment of a War Board in Patiala

Maharaja Yadvinder Singh of Patiala voluntarily offered his personal services and all the resources of the state to Majesty the King Emperor. To implement this offer, a central war board and a local force called Yadvindra Civic Guard, attached to the District and Tehsil committees were established throughout the state. The Civic Guard created in the early 1940's was expanded to other princely state under the British rule. It was prepared according to the auxiliary force present on others princely state. The main purpose of which was to maintain internal security and assist in civil protection. This also included social activities such as carrying out relief work during famines or floods. This organization relected the strategy of the princely states.¹³ The Yadvindra civic guard became an important historical example of how princely state maintained their loyalty to the British Government while asserting their sovereignty through their civil and military initiatives. Captain Raja Baljinder Singh, the younger brother of the Maharaja, was appointed as the Chairman of the war board. By order no. forty three issued from the Moti Bagh palace in Patiala on 23 July 1940, Maharaja Yadvinder Singh established the Patiala War Board which consisted of¹⁴

Members of the Patiala War Board

Name Designation

- Captain Baljinder Singh President
- Sardar D.K.Sen Vice President
- S.Jamil Hussian Junior Vice President
- Col.Rajadhiraj Maheshinder Singh Member
- Captain Kanwar Bharatindra Singh Member
- Captain Nawabzada Afzal Khan Member
- Major General Joginder Singh Member
- Insepector General of Police Member
- Patiala Municipal Committee Member
- Sardar Jaidev Singh Secretary

The involvement of military and legal professionals represents a holistic approach to managing the demands of governance, security and legal affairs in times of war. A report by the Secretary of the war board states that a comprehensive and intensive propaganda campaign has been carried out throughout the state under the auspices of the board, which has already resulted in the recruitment of about 5,000 recruits into the British Indian Army and the collection of about Rs.200000 in donations to the war fund. In addition, the officers and feudal lords of the state have contributed about Rs.700000 to the interest free war loan of the government of India. Maharaja Yadvinder Singh played an exemplary role in supporting the war effort. His personal donations and active mobilization of the resources of his state. His personal contributed included Rs.200000 to the Viceroy's War Fund. He donated Rs.5000 to the Greece Relief Fund and Rs.1000 to the Aircraft Fund through the Shimla District War Committee.¹⁵

Apart from financial support, Yadvinder Singh's personal involvement was reflected in his dedication to inspiring and encouraging his subjects to support the British cause. He undertook an extensive tour of the interior of the state, which was enthusiastically received by the public, further boosting morale and unity. The state's contribution to the war effort also reflected strategic military and humanitarian commitments. It is noteworthy that two infantry units and a lancer regiment were deployed for active duty and the 3rd and 4th Patiala infantry units reached full operational capacity. In addition, the establishment of a training battalion and an army training school ensured that new recruits were properly prepared for military service. On the behalf of the Crown, the state also formed the 56th transport company Patiala, thereby expanding its service to national defence logistics.¹⁶ In the humanitarian sector, under the patronage of Her Majesty the Queen Mahinder Kaur the ladies committee prepared and sent 890 sets of knitwear including sweaters, scarves and socks to Patiala infantry units serving abroad. These contributions both material and moral combine military preparedness, public mobilization and humanitarian sympathy under the active leadership of Maharaja Yadvinder Singh, highlighting the extensive commitment to the state to the war effort. Continuous efforts

to recruits soldiers and raise funds are a feature of activate of the war board and the response from the people of the state was highly commendable.¹⁷

On July 13, 1943, Maharaja Yadvindef Singh directed his Secretary to immediately send Rs.10,000 to the Secretary of the Khalsa Defence League of India. This amount was to settle the dues of the league and was in addition to the increased monthly contribution authorized earlier by order of Maharaja Yadvinder Singh dated May 20,1943 the recurring monthly donation to the league was increased from Rs.1,000 to Rs.5500 effective from April 1,1944. Any additional amount of Rs.10,000 or more shall be considered a supplements grant and arrangements should be made to send the monthly donation to the league secretary during the first week of the each month.¹⁸

Ijlas-I-Khas Office No 26, dated 31st October 1944, Moti Bagh Palace, Patiala wrote to Sardar Gian Singh Rarewala Finance Minister, Patiala to arrange for the transfer of sum of Rs.25000 to the private secretary as a donation to His Excellency the Viceroy's war relief fund. This amount was in addition to Rs.15000 to pay as supplementary grant from the government treasury. Moti Bagh Palace order no 34 refers to the allocation of funds for the Urdu daily newspaper, Ajit Lahore. The order issued under the authority of Maharaja Mahendra Bahadur, directs the Finance Minister to arrange for the payments of Rs.10,000 to the editor of the Urdu newspaper. This amount was to be allocated as a supplementary grant to the newspaper under the category of donations and contributions in the budget of the ministry of external affairs. This order reflects the Maharaja's support for the Urdu press and his interest in promoting the Urdu language. This allocation can be understood as an investment to promote cultural or political relations with the press, which possibly reflects the growing importance of the Urdu press in the context of Indian politics and social movements during the era of independence.¹⁹

According to the *Patiala Post* which was a news supplement published from Patiala. The most difficult problem in the last Great War was that after bringing the soldiers home.²⁰ As soon as the war ended and they were discharged from the army, the soldiers faced many difficulties. They were thrust into a crowded job market without adequate preparation or opportunities. More than 60000 soldiers were sent to war from Patiala state alone. The state government recognized the need to ensure a resumption of life for those who had been left behind. A reconstruction committee was established for this work. There is increasing promise to create a comprehensive work force to equip soldiers with the skills and opportunities they need to thrive in their home environment.²¹

During the war, the Patiala state infantry received several honours and distinctions in recognition of their bravery and dedication. The awards presented included: one Military Cross, order of British India, 2nd class with the tittle of brave-1, order of merit of India, 2nd class-4, Indian distinguished service medal-7, Indian meritorious service medal -1, Gold Medal -1, Silver Medal -1, these honors reflects the courage skill and sacrifice of the battalions in some of the most challenging theatres of the war. The battalions maintained a strong flied strength throughout the war. In the operations in the Burma Malaya 8officers and 228 soldiers were killed of whom 39 were killed.²²

Conclusion

The princely state of Patiala played a significant, through often overlooked role in the Second World War. Its contribution included military recruitment, logistical support, financial assistance and unwavering loyalty to the British Crown. The state mobilized thousands of soldiers of Patiala state alone raised several battalions that actively participated on various fronts .Its troops such as the Patiala state infantry, displayed valor and received several military honours. However the war also brought challenges including widespread desertion, the pressure of conscription on the rural population and post war devastation. After the Second World War, the Princely state faced economic hardship, social unrest and the challenge of reintegrating returning soldiers into civilian life.as they were adjusting to these realities, the shock of partition in 1947 created new and even more complex challenges. Leadership played a crucial role in managing these crises. Maharaja Yadvinder Singh of Patiala in particular showed great administrative acumen in meeting the challenges of the post war period and partition, ensuring a sensible response to the needs of refugees, the Sikh community and the general population. His leadership along with that of the rulers of other princely states highlights the delicate balance maintained by these states between loyalty to the British and their responsibilities to their people.

The contribution of Patiala state in the Second World War, was one of active participation sacrifice and strategic adjustments to the changing political environment. Their wartime contributions not only shaped the military history of British India but also influenced the socio

political behavior of Punjab in the years leading up to independence. The princely state of Patiala fielded well trained and disciplined armies that played a crucial role in the Second World War by actively supporting the British war effort. These armies historically formed to defend their respective states and assist the British Empire, made significant contributions to various military campaigns, providing both men and logistical support.

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